

Social media platforms use content moderators to remove content that violates laws and usage guidelines. In such cases, they are regularly exposed to content such as hate speech, (sexualized) violence, animal cruelty, etc.

Constant exposure to this content carries a high risk of damaging mental health and in many cases leads to depression, anxiety disorders, and post-traumatic stress disorder.

Outsourcing to third world countries, high pressure to perform, low salaries, and lack of psychological support further increase the risks.

Artificial intelligence is still unable to reliably perform content moderation and replace human workers [1, 2].

For millions of influencers and medium-sized companies, social networks are the main source of income or an invaluable advertising platform, and they are therefore financially dependent on social media [3].

The majority of profits go to streaming services and music labels. Artists receive less than 1 cent per stream, which amounts to an average of only around 16% of revenue. [4-6].

The training of artificial intelligence relies on manual classification of training data. These tasks are often outsourced in the form of crowd work.

The jobs are posted on portals and workers are paid per task. Unpaid work, such as searching for suitable jobs, further reduces the low hourly rate, so that the real hourly rate is often less than €4.

Crowd-workers are also exposed to content such as hate speech, animal abuse, (sexual, extremist, ...) violence, ... with consequences comparable to those of content moderation on social networks. [7,8].

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